

Connectivity detection for automatic construction of building geometric digital twins

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ABSTRACT

Existing buildings' geometry digitisation using Point Cloud Datasets is important. This is evident given the lack of digital as-designed models for older buildings, which can serve as a reference for as-is conditions modelling, and their unreliability for newer buildings. However, detecting the connectivity between entities for effective construction of a geometric Digital Twin from Point Cloud Datasets is an unsolved problem. This work defines a new problem, connectivity detection in buildings from Point Cloud Datasets. To solve it, we define a surface topology graph that represents relationships between labelled surfaces and propose a deep-geometric-neural-network-based framework to reconstruct the graph. Extensive experiments on the S3DIS dataset demonstrate that our method achieves high performance in relation detection. The practical application for structural object detection further validates the effectiveness of the proposed approach and highlights the value of relations. The findings of this study contribute to the advancement of the construction of Digital Twins, facilitating the efficient analysis and reasoning of objects, spaces, and entire buildings within the Digital Twin framework.

1. Introduction

Digital Twins (DTs) have shown their importance for operation, maintenance and reconstruction stages of the building lifecycle [1–4]. The geometry of a DT or geometric DT (gDT) plays a vital role in multiple DT applications, such as energy and behavioural simulations [5], autonomous indoor navigation and route planning [6], and floorplan reconstruction, among others. Digitisation of existing buildings' geometry or construction of gDT relies heavily on point clouds. This is because the majority of buildings were constructed more than 20 years ago [7,8], i.e. prior to the wide adoption of Computer-Aided Design (CAD) and Building Information Modelling (BIM). Therefore, the buildings mentioned above do not have any digital as-designed, as-built models to facilitate the digitisation of as-is conditions. Moreover, as-designed models of newer buildings can be outdated and unreliable [9] due to changes during building construction and operation that result in significant differences between the as-designed and as-built states of the building. Alternatively, extracting geometric information from Point Cloud Datasets (PCDs) provides a promising solution for geometry digitisation.

Existing commercial solutions for digitising building geometry from PCDs do not automatically produce gDT. This software can assist in

detecting primitive geometry, such as cuboids and cylinders, and facilitating modelling, but the process is either semi-automatic (e.g. Faro as-built modeller), or the resulting shapes require manual modifications (e.g. EdgeWise Building) [10]. In addition, the output of the automatic tools is unconnected and incoherent. Therefore, manual modelling is required to form a proper building model from the output of such tools. Currently, the costs associated with manual labour during the digitisation of the geometry of existing buildings outweigh the potential benefits of DTs.

Connectivity between entities, i.e. how objects compose a single, consistent structure, is essential for gDT and BIM applications, among various types of geometric information. This statement is shown by a number of studies that utilise relations between entities to extract knowledge. Recent research shows that connectivity and graph representation of buildings are beneficial for various practical applications [11–14]. For example, asset management applications require topological information, and energy simulation/optimisation methods require the association of individual objects and spaces. For instance, topological information can be used to classify spaces based on their intended function, such as identifying hallways, living rooms, kitchens, and other areas [15]. Therefore, establishing relations is an essential step in digitising the geometry of existing buildings.

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Building digitisation requires detecting objects, spaces and relations (Fig. 2). However, existing methods [16,17] can successfully detect and classify surfaces and certain types of objects, they cannot automatically build the connectivity between entities, e.g. establish adjacency and composition relations between them. While the current state of practice and research has traditionally put less emphasis on relation detection, it remains necessary for building digitisation. On top of that, relation detection and object/space detection can boost each other's performance when integrated compared to when performed independently. In Fig. 2, the white arrow highlights that relation detection can guide object/space detection by employing consistency and coherence and vice versa, thus improving the performance of both. Therefore, this paper focuses on geometry digitisation from PCDs, emphasising relation detection.

Surface topology, i.e. how surfaces compose a building and its elements, serves as a basis for other graph representations. Fig. 1 highlights that multiple other representations, from low-level geometric information, such as geometries of individual objects, to high-level building topology are hinged on surfaces. We argue that "same space" and "same object" relations contain necessary information to infer other geometric-based relations between surfaces, objects and spaces. Therefore, we define a surface topology graph in this paper, a graph of surfaces connected together if they belong to the same object or space, to detect the connectivity in an existing building. We propose a framework for graph reconstruction and explain how this graph can be used to reason about objects and spaces, and a building. We reconstruct this graph by relating surfaces using deep geometric neural networks after a set of filtering

Fig. 1. Surface Topology overview.

Fig. 2. Geometry digitisation of existing buildings from PCDs pipeline. Traditionally, only the object/space detection is considered. The relation detection is also necessary and can improve the performance of the object/space detection when integrated.

steps. We evaluate the performance on the Stanford 3D S3DIS dataset and show that our proposed method achieves 97% – 99% Receiver Operating Characteristic Area Under the Curve (ROC AUC) in relation detection. We then highlight the value of the detected relations by detecting structural objects. We summarise the contribution as follows:

- We define a new problem, connectivity detection in an existing building.
- To clarify the connectivity, we further define a surface topology graph and propose a framework to construct it automatically.
- We conduct extensive experiments on the Stanford 3D S3DIS dataset to validate the effectiveness of our proposed method.
- We show a practical application of the detected relations and detect structural objects from PCDs.

2. Background

Relation detection from a PCD aims to identify relations between geometric entities, such as surfaces, objects and spaces, contained in the PCD. This section starts with a review of existing methods for building digitisation, including approaches for the detection of geometric objects. It includes object and space detection methods that implicitly capture this information. Then, we review rule-based and learning-based relation detection methods. We structure this section as follows: first, we review those methods for object and space detection; then, we review rule-based and learning-based methods for relation detection in indoor environments; lastly, we review geometric deep neural network approaches because they help in analysing PCD.

Object detection methods from PCD can be generally split into model-driven and data-driven approaches. The former explicitly defines the mathematical form of an object and finds parameters that fit best into the input PCD. This is usually based on primitive shapes detection, namely planar or cylindrical patches, with RANSAC [18,19], Hough Transform [20] or region-growing segmentation [21,22]. These surfaces are later related using rule-based methods to form individual objects.

Rule-based methods for relation detection between surfaces explicitly define rules on what surfaces or objects are related to each other. It is

used to compose surfaces belonging to the same object [18], or to identify adjacency between objects [23,24], to refine object dimensions among other examples. These methods are specific to the problems and environments they are designed for.

The latter group of methods detects objects by inferring patterns from large sets of labelled datasets. It allows to design of methods that are not necessarily specific to particular environments and can be extended by extending training datasets. A number of works use artificial neural networks (NNs) to digitise buildings [25–27], including large-scale and cluttered PCDs. In practice, this approach detects objects directly from PCDs.

Deep learning approaches for point cloud segmentation [16,17] and object detection [28,29] show decent performance while alleviating drawbacks of model-driven methods. They allow classifying points from the input, detecting surfaces and objects automatically from point clouds. Data-driven approaches can also be used to guide model-driven methods for object detection for better computational efficiency [30]. However, they require extra steps to relate these surfaces/objects with each other to form a building.

Space detection with classical [23,31] and deep learning approaches [16,32] has achieved promising performance. These methods implicitly model relations between objects, spaces or surfaces. In particular, volumetric space and floor plan reconstruction methods contain information to derive building topology.

For example, [33] split space along each axis based on the peaks on projections. They then merged cuboids using the shape-grammar approach. It implicitly provided relations between objects and spaces through adjacency. Still, the scope of the method is limited to Manhattan buildings, meaning that all surfaces are perpendicular to one of the main axes.

Another line of works, including [34,35], reconstructed volumetric models of buildings from point clouds by reducing the problem to 2D (X-Y plane). They detect lines using model-driven methods and split the 2D space into walls and spaces with integer optimisation. They detect vertical surfaces, objects and spaces and detect adjacency and composition relations between them. These methods may require scanner locations and rely on plane/line detection; therefore, they remain sensitive to

Fig. 3. Framework overview.

clutter and occlusions. It is even more influential if significant parts of walls are occluded, which is typical for office environments with many bookshelves. For an in-depth overview of existing approaches for object and space detection authors refer to [10,36].

A number of methods used deep neural networks to predict relations between objects [37,38]. These works use point cloud and graph neural networks to construct and classify edges to infer relations, such as ‘near to’, ‘lying on’, ‘covers’, and ‘part of’, in room-scale point clouds and are not designed for structural elements. A similar approach has been used to do a large-scale semantic segmentation of sets of surfaces by propagating information using graphs [39].

Another line of work reconstructs building-scale scene graphs from imagery data [40,41]. They use visual odometry methods to estimate the 3D geometry of indoor scenes and images to detect objects and spaces. They also use sensor locations to assist in inferring composition relations between entities.

Overall, current research methods in topology reconstruction still rely on rule-based relation detection methods. They are limited by the environmental assumptions in their design and are not directly extendable to other environments. Additionally, methods for topology reconstruction that use plane detection are sensitive to clutter and occlusions as they do not account for that. There are no methods for the reconstruction of relations between objects, spaces and surfaces for large-scale, cluttered point clouds with occlusions.

Summarising recognised gaps in knowledge, the current state of research has not achieved topological relation detection from large-scale PCDs. The existing methods are developed for room-scale scenes, require additional input or use rule-based methods that are not able to capture the variety of cases and are sensitive to clutter and occlusions. The aim of this paper is to provide a generic method for topological relation detection for large-scale scenes.

3. Proposed solution

The proposed method addresses the knowledge gap stated above. It expects a point cloud with labels as input and produces a graph of planar surfaces as output (Eq. 1–3). The edges of the graph are of two types: ‘same space’ and ‘same object’. These relations between surfaces form the basis for topological properties of spaces and objects in a building.

$$G = (V, E), \quad (1)$$

$$V = \{s : s - \text{surface}\}, \quad (2)$$

$$E = \{(e, t_e) : e \in V \times V, t_e \in \{\text{same - space}, \text{same - object}\}\}. \quad (3)$$

Fig. 3 shows the proposed method that consists of the following steps:

- Surface detection
- Neighbour connection and filtration
 - Neighbour connection
 - Line-cast-based rejection
- Neural network edge type prediction

We first need to create nodes for the graph representation. We begin by detecting surfaces from the PCD, aiming to classify pairs of nodes in a relation-agnostic manner. In this way, we can avoid using any information about particular relations. Specifically, we use one of the best-performing 3D neural network architectures for 3D point cloud classification and build a PointNeXt-based model [17] to classify the connectivity between pairs of surfaces directly from PCD. The connectivity detection is sensitive to the ratio of positive to negative pairs, i.e. pairs of surfaces that are in the relation and not in the relation, respectively. However, the number of negative pairs exceeds the number of positive pairs by a large margin. To solve the heavily biased problem, we propose “Neighbour connection” and “Line-cast-based rejection” to filter out unnecessary negative pairs.

Surface detection extracts a set of planar surfaces from the input PCD. Surface detection methods, such as RANSAC and clustering, bloom performance on large-scale inputs. In contrast, floors are always horizontal planar surfaces. Therefore, we start by identifying floor levels on the density histogram along the Z-axis following [42] approach. It allows the extraction of floor points and splitting the PCD of a building into PCDs of individual floors, which are then processed independently for computational efficiency. Then we extract planar surfaces, which can be described with the following eqs. (4, 5) where S_i is i_{th} surface, $B_\gamma(p)$ is a ball of size γ around point p , N_q is a normal of point q , $\|\cdot\|_2$ is L_2 -norm, $|\cdot|$ is a cardinality of a set, PCD is the input PCD, ϵ, γ are parameters. We use a 2-step DBSCAN clustering [43]: 1) normal orientation clustering to ensure that normals of points from one cluster are sufficiently close to each other, 2) XYZ clustering of each cluster to ensure that different surfaces with similar normals are disjoint.

$$S_i = \{p : |B_\gamma(p) \cap PCD| \geq n; \forall q \in B_\gamma(p) \cap S_i : \|N_p - N_q\|_2 < \epsilon\} \quad (4)$$

$$B_\gamma(p) = \{x : \|x - p\|_2 < \gamma\}, \quad (5)$$

Topological-related surfaces that we aim to relate tend to be close to each other. Thus, **Neighbour connection** step constructs a graph of potential relations by connecting each surface if the distance between them is smaller than a predefined threshold. This allows to reduce the

Fig. 4. Example of *visible* and *non-visible* surfaces. Gray - empty space, white - filled space or objects, blue surface - anchor, green surface - visible to anchor, red surface - not visible to anchor, yellow surfaces - obstacle between the blue and red surfaces. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 5. Intersecting a line with a point.

number of potential relations significantly ($O(n)$ for neighbour connected vs $O(n^2)$ for fully connected) and removes a considerable number of non-related pairs of surfaces. As a result, the performance of the following steps is improved.

The distance between two surfaces is defined as the smallest distance between all pairs of points of these two surfaces (Eq. 6). We are considering planar surfaces in this study. In practice, planar surfaces are well approximated by bounding boxes. Therefore, we approximate the distance between two point clusters with a distance between their bounding boxes for computational efficiency.

$$D(A, B) = \min_{a \in A, b \in B} \|a - b\|. \quad (6)$$

Line-cast-based rejection step is designed to deal with a large number of negative pairs produced in the previous step. Such an unbalanced distribution among positive and negative pairs makes training a neural network difficult. We propose line-cast-based rejection to reduce the number of negative pairs further and overcome the stated challenge. The idea is that related surfaces should be “visible” to each other. This assumption holds for all surfaces belonging to an object and for the majority of surfaces belonging to a space interior. It is important to note that although some of the “same-space” relations will be missing, there should always be a few surfaces from the same space that are “visible” to a particular one. In other words, the missing edges will not disconnect a surface from the others in the same space.

In this context, the “visibility” is defined as follows: there is a part of one surface that has nothing between it and a part of the other object (Fig. 4). This is checked by sampling a number of random lines connecting a point from the first surface to a point from the other surface. If there is something along the line it is considered to be an occlusion. The “visibility” score is the number of non-occluded lines divided by the total number of lines.

Table 1
Performance of neural network classifier with the threshold of 0.9.

Dataset/Relation	ROC AUC	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	$\frac{\#positive}{\#negative}$
S3DIS/Same-Space	0.97	0.83	0.97	0.70	1.07
S3DIS/Same-Object	0.99	0.97	0.96	0.82	0.15
TUMCMS/Same-Space	0.56	0.46	0.75	0.08	1.55
TUMCMS/Same-Object	0.63	0.95	0.25	0.26	0.03

(a) Same-Space

(b) Same-Object

Fig. 6. Precision-Recall curve for two types of relations.

Fig. 7. (a) - Empirical CDF of distances between related surfaces. (b) - The fraction of non-recoverable relations at given thresholds.

Fig. 8. Fraction of positive pairs among all pairs within distance.

Each line is checked against other planar surfaces and all other points in the PCD. We need to check that the line connecting two points (denoted as anchors) has no other points (denoted as query) close to it for each pair of points. We also need to take surface orientation around each query point to understand if the line goes nearly parallel to the surface or not, as it influences if the line intersects the surface near the query point or not. Therefore, for each point from the surroundings (query point) we compute if its foot of the perpendicular (projection perpendicular to the normal) to the line lies between anchor points and that the distance between this projection and the point itself is sufficiently small.

We intersect the line with the plane defined by the point and its normal and compute the distance between the intersection and the point and threshold it (Fig. 5). In the following equations, p_1 depicts a point from one of the two surfaces that are checked (anchor points), P depicts a point of the surroundings that may potentially occlude p_2 from p_1 (query point), and N is a normal of the point P . Eq. 7 shows d_{line} which is the distance from p_1 to the point where the line spanned by points p_1 (from one surface) and p_2 (from another surface) intersects the plane spanned by the point P with normal N . Points laying between these two have $0 < d_{line} < 1$. Eq. 8 shows d_{point}^2 the squared distance between the intersection point and point P . d_{line} is then thresholded such as $\varepsilon < d_{line} <$

$1 - \varepsilon$ to verify that the intersection point is between two points and to reject points that are close to one of the ends of the line. It is necessary to reduce the noise in normal estimation of points near to the end of the line. The value of this parameter generally depends on the density of the PCD. In the case of points laying on planar surfaces, we compute the plane only once to reduce the amount of computations.

$$d_{line} = \frac{\sum (P - p_1) \cdot N}{N \cdot (p_2 - p_1)}, \quad (7)$$

$$d_{point}^2 = \sum (P - d_{line} \cdot (p_2 - p_1) + p_1) \cdot (P - d_{line} \cdot (p_2 - p_1) + p_1). \quad (8)$$

We keep those pairs of surfaces that have d_{line} , d_{point} within the above-mentioned thresholds. We also keep surfaces that lie on the same plane. This is necessary because some of them may be “invisible” to each other due to noise, even though they are related. We then classify each remaining pair of surfaces.

The previous steps generate a number of surface pairs that may or may not be related. We are required to classify each pair while not explicitly exploiting specifics of particular relations in consideration. Therefore, we design the **neural network edge type prediction** step that classifies each remaining pair. The relations between two objects are defined by local geometry, i.e., the geometry of the neighbourhood and by the composition of multiple objects. We incorporate geometric hints in edge classification by sub-sampling the original point cloud inside a bounding box that includes both surfaces and two surface masks to convey local geometry.

We then classify this sub-sampled point cloud by using a Point-NeXt-based architecture [17]. This model is selected because it provides one of the best performances for semantic segmentation of PCDs of indoor environments. In order to obtain the classification of the input sample, we predict probability-like values for all relation types. Therefore, we train the model using binary cross entropy (Eq. 9) on ground truth labels. The probability-like values are obtained using the sigmoid function on top of the neural network output.

$$L = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_n \left[y_n \cdot \ln \sigma(f(x_n, \theta)) + (1 - y_n) \cdot \ln \left(1 - \sigma(f(x_n, \theta)) \right) \right], \quad (9)$$

where f denotes neural network, θ - learnable parameters, x_n and y_n denotes point cloud and ground-truth label of n -th sample, respectively).

Fig. 9. (a), (b) - examples of a line between two surfaces from one space hitting a point on a chair. (c) - example of 100 lines between two surfaces from one space, (d) - example of 100 lines between two surfaces from different spaces; red lines hit something, green lines do not hit.

Table 2

Performance of Line-cast-based rejection step at visibility threshold of 25%.

Relation	Rejected positives	Rejected negatives	$\frac{\#positive}{\#negative}$ before	$\frac{\#positive}{\#negative}$ after
Both	24.6%	70.5%	0.55	1.41
Same-Space	25.1%	67.5%	0.46	1.07
Same-Object	9.7%	57.3%	0.07	0.15

4. Experiments

We conduct the experiments on Stanford 3D S3DIS dataset [44] to validate the effectiveness of our proposed method, which is expected to handle large-scale and occluded point clouds. The dataset contains six point clouds representing six storeys of multiple buildings and covers more than 6000 square metres of area. These point clouds are highly cluttered and large-scale. Among these six storeys, the 5th one is the largest and most challenging sample in the dataset. Therefore, we used the 5th storey for evaluation and the other 5 stories for training. First, we report the overall performance of the method; then, we report the performances of individual steps.

We chose Python 3.8 to implement the proposed method because it has a number of useful libraries. We used the following libraries: Numpy [45] for mathematics, PyTorch [46] and PyTorch Geometric [47] for training and inferencing 3D neural networks, Scipy [48] and Sklearn

[49] for spatial algorithms, such as DBSCAN clustering, Kd trees and KNN classification, Open3D [50] for 3D visualisation and Matplotlib [51] for 2D visualisation. We used a computer with AMD Ryzen 5 5600× CPU, Nvidia GTX 2070 Super GPU, 32GB RAM for the experiments.

4.1. Neural network classification

The neural network was trained on areas 1, 2, 3, 4, and 6 of the S3DIS dataset. We left 10 % of the training samples selected randomly for validation to fine-tune training hyper-parameters, such as the number of epochs. We observe that 150 epochs allow validation metrics, such as the value of the loss function, accuracy, precision and recall, to level out. We stop at 150 epochs to prevent overfitting.

We also employ random augmentations, namely random rotations around the Z-axis, random shifts of a sample to up to one metre in a random directions, random noise to point coordinates and point features, setting features of 15% of random points to zero, to further prevent overfitting. In addition to that, each batch was split into four equal parts between positive and negative samples for both types of relations. This was necessary to alleviate the imbalance of the training dataset. We also used hard negative sampling to speed up the convergence of the training process. It means that we selected samples at random but proportionally to the loss the sample gave the last time. We also reset the last loss for each sample every ten epochs to allow more diversity.

Fig. 6 shows the precision-recall curve for both types of relations. The neural network achieved 97% and 99% ROC AUC for “same-space” and “same-object” relations, respectively. These results clearly indicate the high accuracy of the selected classifier. We thresholded scores at 0.9 to

Fig. 10. Two examples of positive pairs that are not “visible” to each other. (a), (b) - example for a wall and the vertical surface of a beam; (c), (d) - example of a wall and a column surfaces. Green and blue bounding boxes represent two surfaces of a positive pair. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

minimise false-positive detections, as false-negative detections can be dealt with using the transitivity of the relations.

We also evaluated this step on the TUMCMS dataset [52] to check how well it generalises on other environments. We keep the same model trained on S3DIS Areas 1, 2, 3, 4, and 6 and evaluate on TUMCMS. Table 1 provides the performance of the classifier on both datasets (Area 5 for S3DIS and TUMCMS). It is clearly seen that the performance on the TUMCMS is notably smaller than on S3DIS. This is because the environment has significant deviations, for example, due to the different construction practices and indoor design in the US and Germany. This behaviour is also observed in other scenarios and with other neural network architectures [31].

4.2. Neighbour connection

Fig. 7a shows the empirical CDF of distances between related relations. Large distances for “same-space” relation correspond to larger spaces, such as long corridors. Likewise, large distances for “same-object” relations correspond to long walls of these corridors, which have multiple surfaces. The figure clearly shows that there is a large portion of distant surfaces that are related.

However, these relations are transitive. It means that even if one of the relations is missing, but there is a path between the two surfaces, the relation can be recovered through the chain of others. Therefore, we computed the number of relations that could not be recovered if we

considered only pairs of surfaces within the threshold. Fig. 7b shows the portion of relations that would not be recoverable at different thresholds. It shows that a 2.5-m threshold keeps over 99.8% of “same-object” relations and over 98.1% of “same-space” relations while drastically reducing the total number of pairs. Therefore, we kept only those pairs that are within the 2.5-m distance between surfaces.

Fig. 8 provides the fraction of positive pairs among all pairs within distance. It shows that the selected threshold keeps roughly the same number of positive and negative pairs for “same space” relation and increases the ratio for “same object”. This has a good impact on the neural network classification step of the method.

4.3. Line-cast-based rejection

We sampled 12,288 points uniformly from the bounding box that includes both objects for each potential relation. We then randomly picked 100 pairs of points and performed a “visibility” check. Fig. 9 shows a few examples of a random line between two surfaces from the same space hitting furniture (a-b); and top-down view on a 100 lines between two surfaces from the same space (c) and between two surfaces from different spaces (d). We chose 25% visibility score as a threshold because it reduces the number of pairs while keeping the number of non-recoverable relations low, being 0.008% and 0.3% for “same-space” and “same-object”, respectively.

Fig. 11. Example of the topology graph. Blue - belong to the same space, and green - belong to the same object. (a) - Nodes of surfaces, (b) - Relations between surfaces, (c) - Connected components in the graph, (d) - Dual graph of objects and spaces.

Fig. 12. Example of partial detection inside one space. Green lines depict true-positive detections; Red lines depict false-negative detections. All surfaces from the example are in the same connected component. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 2 shows the performance of this step in terms of the number of rejected positive (those that are related) and negative (those that are not related) pairs. It is clearly seen that the proposed step filters out a substantial part of the negative pairs while keeping most of the positive pairs in place. Fig. 10 shows typical examples of positive pairs from the same space that are rejected because they are not “visible” to each other, and, therefore, rejected. A closer inspection of rejected positive pairs

showed that 99.87% and 97.0% of rejected pairs still remain within three hops between surfaces for “same-space” and “same-object” relations, respectively.

5. Case-study: Space and object detection

In this section, we evaluate a practical application of the presented approach. To demonstrate the value of the detected relations. We used the results of the proposed framework to detect objects and spaces. The individual objects and spaces were derived as connected components of corresponding relations. Connected components of different relations share nodes - surfaces that separate these two connected components.

Each surface from a point cloud is a boundary between an object and a space. Therefore, it belongs to exactly one object and exactly one space. The set of surfaces connected by the above-mentioned relations spans a graph of connected surfaces, also referred to as the *surface topology graph*. Each node in the *surface topology graph* introduces the relation between an object and a space. This spans a dual graph or *object-space topology graph*, where each connected component is a node representing an object or a space, and each surface is an edge representing the adjacency relation. Fig. 11 shows an example of the graphs and their duality.

The chosen representation has an important property: it is tolerant of the presence of false-negative relations to some extent. It does not require a connected component to be fully connected. This is because false-negative relations can be established transitively by connecting all nodes of the topology graph if they belong to the same connected component. As such, missing relations between some pairs of surfaces do not influence space or object detection as long as the set of surfaces remains connected (Fig. 12), i.e. the minimum number of detected relations is $O(n)$ edges for n nodes in contrast to the ground truth $O(n^2)$ edges. This is more evident for spaces than objects because the former has more surfaces than the latter. Therefore, the parameters of the

Fig. 13. Precision-Recall curve for space and object detection on different IoU thresholds.

Table 3

Object detection performance comparison for structural objects. Average Precision (AP), Average Recall (AR), and mean Average Precision (mAP) at mIoU of 0.5.

	AP@0.5	AR@0.5	mAP@0.5
FCAF3D	49.6%	66.0%	–
CorDet	–	–	82.7%
Our	93.3%	96.3%	87.4%

Table 4

Detection of spaces and objects with connected components analysis (percentage of total).

	Correct	Over-segmented	Under-segmented
Spaces	35%	37%	37%
Objects	90%	5%	5%

Table 5

Performance of the approach with different steps.

	Same-Space		Same-Object	
	Precision	Recall	Precision	Recall
<i>Dist(5m)&NN</i>	81.4%	64.8%	80.0%	43.4%
<i>Dist(2.5m)&NN</i>	95.5%	70.2%	93.9%	80.7%
<i>Dist(2.5m)&LC&NN</i>	97.4%	70.0%	95.9%	81.8%

relation detection were optimised to minimise false-positive detections, as they are harder to deal with in the context of this case study.

Fig. 13 shows the precision and recall graphs for spaces and objects on multiple thresholds of Intersection over Union (IoU) between ground truth and predicted entities. Table 4 shows how many spaces or objects (entities) have 100% overlap with the predicted ones (correct), how many ground truth entities fell into multiple predicted ones (over-segmented) and how many predicted objects contain multiple ground truth objects (under-segmented).

The experiments showed that this approach can successfully find most objects. However, it needs further processing to detect spaces precisely. A closer inspection of under-segmented spaces highlighted that only 14.6% of rooms merged with a neighbouring one, the same number of rooms merged with corridors they were attached to. A significant fraction of under-segmented spaces are multiple hallways being merged together, which can be explained by little-to-no geometric boundaries between hallways and a disproportionately high number of

them in comparison with training data. 56.7% of over-segmented spaces were split into two parts, while 20% were split into three parts. This was caused by choosing aggressive thresholds to minimise the number of false-positive predictions.

We also compared the results for objects with other object detection works in detecting planar structural objects, namely walls, doors, columns and beams. We compared our method with the state-of-the-art general-purpose object detector FCAF3D [53] and state-of-the-art Scan-to-BIM object detector CorDet [28] on S3DIS dataset. Table 3 shows the average object precision, recall, and mean average precision at the intersection-over-union of 0.5. It is clearly seen that the proposed method outperformed other object detection methods even when applied to large-scale inputs. This means that relation detection is beneficial to address more challenging problems [17].

The evaluation on the TUMCMS dataset gave a similar result. Roughly 70.2% of objects were correctly detected after neural network prediction threshold finetuning, while spaces were mainly under-segmented. This is due to the poorer performance of the neural network classifier on the TUMCMS dataset.

6. Discussion

We evaluated how individual steps influence the final result of relation detection and of the case study in order to justify filtering steps. Table 5 shows the overall performance with different distance thresholding (*Dist*(·)), and line-cast-based rejection (*LC*). The figures show that distance thresholding gives a significant boost to the relation detection framework. Additionally, Line-cast-based rejection further improves precision. It is worth noting that this 2% increase resulted in a notable increase of 6% in the number of correctly detected spaces in the case study.

Both filtering steps are necessary to reduce the number of false pairs and make the positive pairs and negative pairs balanced. This is because the number of negative pairs is much larger than the number of positive pairs. The proposed filtering steps decreased the ratio of positive:negative from 1:8 and 1:20 to roughly 1:1 and 1:4 for “same-space” and “same-object” relations, respectively. This had a positive impact on the overall performance of the method.

Fig. 14 shows some typical examples of correct and incorrect classifications for both types of relations. It is seen that the neural network tend misclassify samples if two surfaces are distant and, therefore, their extended bounding box spans larger space. In this case, the local neighbourhood that is fed to the neural network along with both

Fig. 14. Examples for True Positive (TP) detections, False Positive (FP) detections and False Negative (FN) detections. Red and green depict two surfaces, black or gray depicts background visible for the neural network. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

surfaces is larger in scale, thus, has more objects and clutter inside, which make harder for the neural network to differentiate between different classes. Unifying the scale of the input, such as cropping a same size bounding box inside the current one, can improve overall performance further.

The overall performance of the proposed method can detect topological relations between surfaces well. It captured the environment similar to the training set well but struggled to generalise to other environments. It indicates that more diverse labelled data may be beneficial, which is consistent with findings for semantic segmentation [31].

The evaluation of the object detection method based on the identified relations shows that it can correctly find more than 90% of all structural objects in the PCD from the dataset similar to the training dataset. However, experiments on the TUMCMS dataset, which

represent different indoor environments, show that practical applications of the proposed method would achieve roughly 80% of the performance in comparison with the training dataset. This indicates the demand for diversifying a training dataset to cover a wider range of environments for better utilisation of the proposed approach in practical scenarios.

The better performance of object detection in comparison with space detection in the case study is caused by a significantly larger number of surfaces that belong to a single space interior. The proposed method for space detection is sensitive to false-positive relation detection. Therefore, 3% of incorrect positive detection resulted in a notable drop in space detection. A probabilistic approach to clustering surfaces can improve the overall detection. In contrast, most objects were correctly detected because they usually consist of two to three surfaces.

There are a few limitations of the proposed method. First, the method requires point labels as input, which assumes extra preprocessing steps after data acquisition. This entails either a manual correction of semantic segmentation of an NN trained on public datasets, because the state-of-the-art NNs cannot achieve high results for all structural objects, or access to large labelled datasets to train the NN for a much better performance of automatic semantic segmentation.

Second, the conducted experiments show that the proposed method struggles to generalise on any data when trained on the S3DIS dataset only. This indicates the demand for larger labelled datasets that cover a larger variety of environments. Alternatively, labelled datasets that are automatically generated from BIM models can be used to expand and diversify existing datasets. Several studies show that such a technique can bridge the gap for NN-based approaches with limited real-world datasets [54,55]. This approach can also help deal with the first limitation by improving automatic semantic segmentation or enlarging training datasets for the proposed method and removing labels from the input.

7. Conclusions and future work

The paper presented a problem formulation for 3D topological information detection from PCDs of buildings. We then proposed a method for automatic detection of relations between surfaces in large-scale PCDs. The method for detecting and classifying relations showed excellent performance, achieving ROC AUC scores ranging from 97% to 99%.

We showed that “same-space” and “same-object” relations between surfaces can be used to derive different graph representations based on the geometry of a building. The value of detected relations has been demonstrated in the context of structural object detection. A simple post-processing step managed to outperform other methods for structural object detection in indoor environments. This highlights that the proposed relations detected automatically can improve geometry digitisation in the broader context and reduce overheads associated with digitising existing facilities.

The proposed method effectively identifies relationships within PCDs. With this, the results from building digitisation software can be processed more efficiently. Specifically, the detected surfaces can be automatically grouped into objects more easily. The method also supports automatic identification of how objects in buildings relate to each other. This is important since these relationships are an essential component of a DT and are required by different DT applications. By automating these processes, less time and effort are necessary for modelling the geometry of existing buildings. This implies lower costs for constructing gDTs of non-digitised assets.

The proposed method makes a step forward from existing software solutions on the market and other research methods in digitising building geometry. It complements and extends their output by stitching together an unordered set of detected surfaces, decreasing further manual effort in digitising existing assets. Reduced costs in digitising existing facilities make DTs more profitable on a wider scale. This encourages the adoption of digital methods in managing older buildings. As a result, the expenses related to the maintenance and operation of these assets decrease. The examples include better data management, environmental impact, safety of buildings. Subsequently, this boosts the productivity of the sector, leading to an enhanced overall economy.

In the future, we aim to expand the proposed method to handle surfaces and objects of all shapes and then test the presented method on them. This would allow us to work with a wide variety of objects. Additionally, we are looking to apply our relation detection to different kinds of relations. Also, we plan to use the detected relations to derive various graph representations of buildings, including those mentioned Fig. 1. These experiments would demonstrate that the method can handle various objects and relations, bridging current gaps in knowledge in digitising existing building geometry.

Another potential research direction is to combine relation detection with the identification of objects and spaces. By combining these techniques, we can leverage the advantages of each to mitigate their individual limitations. This approach might enhance the performance of methods for both problems. Moreover, it could lead to creating interconnected building models directly from large, obstructed PCDs of existing structures in a seamless manner.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Viktor Drobnyi: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Shuyan Li:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Ioannis Brilakis:** Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

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